

DEPENDENCE OF OPTICAL ACTIVITY ON CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION.
PART I. SALTS OF ACETIC, PROPIONIC, BUTYRIC, PHENYLACETIC,
 β -PHENYLPROPIONIC AND CINNAMIC ACIDS WITH CINCHONIDINE

BY MAGHAR SINGH MANHAS AND KALI KUMAR SHUKLA

Cinchonidine salts of acetic, propionic, butyric, phenylacetic, β -phenylpropionic and cinnamic acids have been prepared. The rotatory dispersion of the above has been examined in methanol, ethanol, chloroform and pyridine. The effect of solvent and some constitutional factors like homologous series, unsaturation and the presence of a phenyl group on the rotatory power has also been explored.

In view of the conflicting results obtained by earlier investigators on the rotatory powers, using several varieties of optically active compounds (Frankland, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 654; 1899, 75, 347; 1893, 63, 511, 1410; Hilditch, *ibid.*, 1909, 95, 1581; Rupe, *Annalen*, 1909, 369, 311; Singh, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 30A, 87, *et seq*), the present authors have selected alkaloids of the cinchona family to provide the asymmetric centre in all the optically active compounds of this series and have undertaken a study of their optical properties.

The present work includes the preparation of cinchonidine salts of acetic, propionic, butyric, phenylacetic, β -phenylpropionic and cinnamic acids. The rotatory dispersion of these salts in different solvents has been studied. The work also incorporates the study of the effect of constitutional factors like homologous series, unsaturation and the presence of phenyl group on the rotatory power of optically active compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

The cinchonidine salts of different acids were prepared by dissolving equimolecular proportions of the alkaloid and the acid separately and then mixing the two solutions together. The salts separating after cooling and scratching were then repeatedly crystallised from ethanol or mixtures of organic solvents as white needles. These salts are freely soluble in chloroform and pyridine, less so in methanol and ethanol, sparingly soluble in ethyl acetate and acetone and practically insoluble in non-polar solvents. The purity of these compounds was tested by their elementary analysis.

TABLE I

No.	Cinchonidine salts.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.
1.	Acetate	.. 125°	8.13	7.91
2.	Propionate	.. 140°	7.84	7.61
3.	Butyrate	.. 85-87°	7.18	7.33
4.	Phenylacetate	.. 144°	6.23	6.51
5.	β -Phenylpropionate	.. 142°	6.56	6.31
6.	Cinnamate	.. 157°	6.28	6.33

The rotatory power determinations were carried out in the visible region of the spectrum for eleven wave-lengths in a 2 dcm polarimeter tube at room temperature (30°). The results are recorded in Tables II to VII.

TABLE II
Cinchonidine acetate.

Solvent : Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	Pyridine 0.5000	EtOH 0.5000	MeOH 0.5000	CHCl ₃ 0.5000	
Calc. {	[α] ..	$\frac{11.33}{\lambda^2 - 0.0640}$	$\frac{21.10}{\lambda^2 - 0.0834}$	$\frac{29.53}{\lambda^2 - 0.0519}$	$\frac{35.57}{\lambda^2 - 0.0353}$
	λ ₀ ..	0.2530	0.2888	0.2278	0.1879
Lines.	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	
Li ₈₇₀₈	-29.00°	-58.00°	-74.00°	-86.00°	
Cd ₆₄₂₈	32.00	64.00	82.00	94.00	
Li ₆₁₀₄	37.00	72.00	92.00	105.00	
Na ₅₈₉₃	40.00	80.00	100.00	114.00	
Hg ₅₇₈₀	42.00	84.00	104.00	119.00	
Hg ₅₄₆₁	48.00	98.00	120.00	136.00	
Cd ₅₀₉₅	58.00	120.00	142.00	159.00	
Cd ₄₇₉₉	68.00	144.00	166.0	182.00	
Cd ₄₆₇₆	73.00	156.00	176.00	194.00	
Li ₄₅₀₂	77.00	164.00	184.00	201.00	
Hg ₄₃₃₈	90.00	198.00	214.00	230.00	

TABLE III

Cinchonidine propionate.

Solvent : Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	Pyridine 0.5000	EtOH 0.5000	MeOH 0.5000	CHCl ₃ 0.5000	
Calc. {	[α] ..	$\frac{10.60}{\lambda^2 - 0.1169}$	$\frac{27.83}{\lambda^2 - 0.0542}$	$\frac{34.96}{\lambda^2 - 0.0233}$	$\frac{37.00}{\lambda^2 - 0.0389}$
	λ ₀ ..	0.3420	0.2328	0.1526	0.1972
Lines.	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	
Li ₈₇₀₈	-32.00°	-70.00°	-82.00°	-90.00°	
Cd ₆₄₂₈	35.00	77.00	89.00	98.00	
Li ₆₁₀₄	41.00	87.00	100.00	110.00	
Na ₅₈₉₃	46.00	95.00	108.00	120.00	
Hg ₅₇₈₀	48.00	99.00	112.00	125.00	
Hg ₅₄₆₁	58.00	114.00	127.00	142.00	
Cd ₅₀₉₅	75.00	136.00	148.00	168.00	
Cd ₄₇₉₉	93.00	158.00	169.00	193.00	
Cd ₄₆₇₆	104.00	169.00	179.00	205.00	
Li ₄₅₀₂	112.00	177.00	185.00	214.00	
Hg ₄₃₃₈	145.00	205.00	210.00	245.00	

TABLE IV

Cinchonidine butyrate.

Solvent :	Pyridine	EtOH	CHCl ₃	MeOH	
Conc. (g./100c.c.) :	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	
Calc. {	[α] ..	$\frac{13.27}{\lambda^2 - 0.1015}$	$\frac{31.93}{\lambda^2 - 0.0342}$	$\frac{38.79}{\lambda^2 - 0.0441}$	$\frac{39.90}{\lambda^2 - 0.0202}$
	λ ₀ ..	0.3187	0.1849	0.2100	0.1421
Lines.	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	
Li ₅₇₀₄	-38.00°	-77.00°	-95.00°	-93.00°	
Cd ₅₄₂₈	42.00	83.00	105.00	101.00	
Li ₅₁₉₄	49.00	94.00	118.00	113.00	
Na ₅₁₂₃	54.00	102.00	128.00	122.00	
Hg ₅₇₈₀	57.00	106.00	134.00	127.00	
Hg ₅₄₆₁	68.00	121.00	152.00	143.00	
Cd ₅₀₄₅	84.00	142.00	181.00	167.00	
Cd ₄₇₉₉	103.00	163.00	208.00	190.00	
Cd ₄₆₇₈	113.00	173.00	222.00	201.00	
Li ₄₈₀₂	120.00	180.00	233.00	208.00	
Hg ₄₂₈₈	150.00	205.00	266.00	235.00	

TABLE V

Cinchonidine phenylacetate.

Solvent :	Pyridine	EtOH	MeOH	CHCl ₃	
Conc. (g./100 c.c.) :	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	
Calc. {	[α] ..	$\frac{7.32}{\lambda^2 - 0.1038}$	$\frac{22.20}{\lambda^2 - 0.0712}$	$\frac{28.95}{\lambda^2 - 0.0487}$	$\frac{32.09}{\lambda^2 - 0.0326}$
	λ ₀ ..	0.3221	0.2263	0.2207	0.1806
Lines.	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	
Li ₅₇₀₄	-22.00°	-56.00°	-72.00°	-77.00°	
Cd ₅₄₂₈	24.00	61.00	80.00	84.00	
Li ₅₁₀₄	27.00	69.00	90.00	94.00	
Na ₅₁₂₃	30.00	75.00	97.00	102.00	
Hg ₅₇₈₀	32.00	78.00	101.00	106.00	
Hg ₅₄₆₁	37.00	90.00	116.00	121.00	
Cd ₅₀₄₅	47.00	107.00	138.00	162.00	
Cd ₄₇₉₉	58.00	124.00	150.00	172.00	
Cd ₄₆₇₈	63.00	132.00	170.00	189.00	
Li ₄₈₀₂	68.00	138.00	177.00	204.00	
Hg ₄₂₈₈	85.00	160.00	205.00		

TABLE VI

Cinchonidine β-phenylpropionate.

Solvent :	Pyridine	EtOH	MeOH	CHCl ₃	
Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	
Calc. {	[α] ..	$\frac{4.948}{\lambda^2 - 0.1239}$	$\frac{18.54}{\lambda^2 - 0.0575}$	$\frac{25.95}{\lambda^2 - 0.0589}$	$\frac{29.41}{\lambda^2 - 0.0531}$
	λ ₀ ..	0.3520	0.2398	0.2427	0.2304
Lines.	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	
Li ₄₇₀₆	- 15.00°	- 48.00°	- 66.00°	- 74.00°	
Cd ₆₄₃₄	17.00	52.00	74.00	81.00	
Li ₅₁₀₄	20.00	58.00	82.00	92.00	
Na ₅₀₉₃	22.00	64.00	90.00	100.00	
Hg ₆₇₈₀	24.00	68.00	94.00	105.00	
Hg ₅₄₆₁	28.00	78.00	108.00	120.00	
Hg ₅₀₄₅	36.00	92.00	130.00	143.00	
Cd ₄₇₈₉	46.00	108.00	152.00	166.00	
Cd ₄₄₇₅	52.00	114.00	162.00	177.00	
Li ₄₀₀₂	56.00	120.00	170.00	185.00	
Hg ₄₂₅₅	75.00	140.00	198.00	215.00	

TABLE VII

Cinchonidine cinnamate.

Solvent :	Pyridine	EtOH	MeOH	CHCl ₃	
Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	0.5000	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	
Calc. {	[α] ..	$\frac{8.10}{\lambda^2 - 0.1225}$	$\frac{26.43}{\lambda^2 - 0.0326}$	$\frac{35.05}{\lambda^2 - 0.0551}$	$\frac{37.69}{\lambda^2 - 0.0572}$
	λ ₀ ..	0.3500	0.1805	0.2347	0.2392
Lines.	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	Obs. [α].	
Li ₄₇₀₆	- 25.00°	- 64.00°	- 88.00°	- 96.00°	
Cd ₆₄₃₅	28.00	70.00	98.00	106.00	
Li ₅₁₀₄	32.00	78.00	110.00	120.00	
Na ₅₀₉₃	36.00	84.00	120.00	130.00	
Hg ₆₇₈₀	38.00	88.00	126.00	136.00	
Hg ₅₄₆₁	46.00	100.00	144.00	156.00	
Cd ₅₀₈₅	59.00	116.00	172.00	188.00	
Cd ₄₇₈₉	75.00	134.00	200.00	218.00	
Cd ₄₄₇₅	84.00	142.00	214.00	234.00	
Li ₄₀₀₂	91.00	148.00	224.00	244.00	
Hg ₄₂₅₅	120.00	168.00	260.00	284.00	

DISCUSSION

Nature of Rotatory Dispersion.—The dispersion is found to be "simple" as it obeys Drude's one-term equation :

$$[\alpha] = \frac{K}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$$

In this equation K and λ_0 are constants and represent the absolute rotation of the substance and the wave-length of the dominant absorption band of its molecule in the ultraviolet region of the spectrum respectively.

TABLE VIII

†No.	[α] ₅₄₆₁ ³⁰			
	CHCl ₃ *(5.2)	Pyridine (12.4)	EtOH (25.8)	MeOH (31.2)
1.	-136.0° (37.57)**	-48.00° (11.33)	-98.00° (21.10)	-120.0° (29.53)
2.	142.0 (37.00)	58.00 (10.60)	114.0 (27.83)	127.0 (34.98)
3.	152.0 (38.79)	68.00 (13.27)	121.0 (31.93)	143.0 (39.90)
4.	121.0 (32.09)	37.00 (7.32)	90.00 (22.20)	116.0 (28.95)
5.	120.0 (29.41)	28.00 (4.948)	78.00 (18.54)	108.00 (25.95)
6.	156.0 (37.69)	46.00 (8.10)	100.0 (26.43)	144.0 (35.05)

*The figures in the brackets refer to the dielectric constant of the solvent.

**The figures in the brackets refer to the rotation constant, K .

†The number of the compounds corresponds to those in Table I.

Effect of Solvent on the Rotatory Power.—From Table VIII it appears that $[\alpha]_{5461}^{30}$ of cinchonidine salts in the four solvents decreases with the corresponding increase in the dielectric constant of the solvent. Chloroform stands out as an exception in all cases.

Rule *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 674, 2652; 1932, 1400, 1409, 2332; 1933, 376, 1217) undertook an extensive study of the change of optical rotatory power caused by solvents. Whatever regularity in the change of rotations with the change of solvents that could be achieved has been correlated with the dipole moment values of the solvents. However, there are many exceptions and no precise inference can possibly be arrived at.

A reference to the present work indicates that all the salts of cinchonidine show the highest value of rotation in chloroform and lowest in pyridine. The values in methanol and ethanol are intermediate between these two extremes. Almost identical conclusions have been arrived at for the change of rotatory power values of quinine salts in these solvents by Manhas and Banerjee (this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 865). Therefore it is difficult to attribute the change in the rotatory power values to the dipole moment of the solvents in question only.

Earlier works of Manhas and Banerjee on brucine salts (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1957, 26A, 285; *J. Univ. Saugar*, 1957, 6, 23; *Res. Bull. Chem. Soc. Univ. Saugar*, 1958, 1, 13; this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 669) and a more recent study undertaken by Perti *et al.* (private communication)

on strychnine salts of substituted aromatic acids show that both these series of compounds exhibit the highest rotation in pyridine.

As compounds with similar constitution are found to behave almost analogously in different solvents as regards their rotatory effect, it seems reasonable to conclude that the constitution of the solvent with respect to that of the optically active solute may also have an important bearing in determining its rotatory power.

Effect of Homologous Series.—Hilditch (*loc. cit.*) has studied the menthyl esters of aliphatic dibasic acids and has come to the conclusion that there is a decrease of rotation in passing from the first to the second, and after that an increase up to the fifth member whereas in the case of bromide salts of these acids, the value goes on increasing up to the third and from there decreases *via* fourth, up to the fifth member of the series.

Frankland (*loc. cit.*) in reviewing the work of earlier investigators states that in ascending series of optically active esters of amyl alcohol and menthol with aliphatic monobasic acids, the values of molecular rotation increase with the molecular weight of the compound up to the third or fourth member of the series and then attain almost a constant value.

Evidently Hilditch's results are at variance with Frankland's observations and, hence, it seems desirable to further study the change of rotatory power in ascending a homologous series.

Table IX records the values of $[M]_{5461}^{30}$, the molecular rotatory power, of the salts of cinchonidine with acetic, propionic and butyric acids in different solvents.

TABLE IX

Cinchonidine salts.	$[M]_{5461}^{30}$			
	CHCl ₃ .	Pyridine.	EtOH.	MeOH.
Acetate	-481.4°	-169.5°	-346.9°	-424.8°
Propionate	522.5	213.4	419.5	467.3
Butyrate	580.6	259.7	462.2	546.3

A comparison of these values shows that as molecular weight of the compound in this homologous series increases, there is a gradual enhancement in the molecular rotation. These results are in agreement with Frankland's observations where a similar increase in the rotatory power has been noted.

Effect of Phenyl Group.—Frankland (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 511, 1410; 1899, 75, 347) has further stated that the molecular rotation in homologous series increases to an approximately constant value on ascending the series, but this rule does not hold good if an aromatic group is situated at some distance from the asymmetric carbon atom. Phenyl group in close proximity to the optically active part of the molecule exercises a disturbing influence on the latter, but the variation depends entirely on the relative position of the aromatic group, and almost disappears if the group is not in the immediate neighbourhood of the asymmetric atom.

Rupe and Wolfleben (*Annalen*, 1913, 395, 136) discussing the optical rotatory power of several esters of *d*-carvoxime conclude that the entrance of a phenyl group into acetic acid or phenylacetic acid or the replacement of methyl by phenyl in acetic acid or crotonic acid diminishes the rotatory power of carvoxime; the entrance of phenyl into α and β positions in cinnamic acid increases the rotatory power. Just the reverse behaviour is observed with the menthyl esters of the acids.

It appears from this work that the replacement of hydrogen atom by a phenyl group in an optically active compound produces a change in the rotatory power. However, it is difficult to say whether this type of change in the constitution of the molecule will lead to an enhancement of rotation or its lowering.

TABLE X

Cinchonidine salts.	$[M]_{5461}^{30^\circ}$			
	CHCl ₃ .	Pyridine.	EtOH.	MeOH.
Acetate	-481.4°	-169.9°	-346.9°	-424.8°
Phenylacetate	520.3	159.1	387.0	499.0
Propionate	522.5	213.4	419.5	467.3
β -Phenylpropionate	532.8	124.3	346.3	479.5

The results of such measurements by the authors on some of the cinchonidine salts are recorded in Table X. It will be observed that with the exception of pyridine, the values of $[M]_{5461}^{30^\circ}$ are higher for cinchonidine phenylacetate than for the acetate salt in all the solvents. However, the comparison of the values of molecular rotation of the propionate and β -phenylpropionate shows that the phenyl salt has higher values in chloroform and methanol whereas in pyridine and ethanol the values are lower than the corresponding values of the propionate. These results also indicate that introduction of the phenyl group does not produce a uniform change in the molecular rotatory power of the asymmetric molecule.

However, a comparison of the values of $[\alpha]_{5461}^{30^\circ}$ shows that the introduction of the phenyl group in place of hydrogen atom leads to a lowering of the rotation values in all cases and in all solvents (Table VIII).

Effect of Unsaturation.—The general consensus of opinion is that the introduction of unsaturation introduces an irregularity in the rotatory power and, in general, the unsaturated linkage leads to a higher rotation.

Pickard and Kenyon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **99**, 45) while comparing the molecular rotatory powers of the esters and salts of phenylpropionic acid and cinnamic acid have also come to the same conclusion. This is supported by the work of later investigators also.

TABLE XI

Cinchonidine salts.	$[M]_{5461}^{30^\circ}$			
	CHCl ₃ .	Pyridine.	EtOH.	MeOH.
β -Phenylpropionate	-532.8°	-124.3°	-346.3°	-479.5°
Cinnamate	689.5	203.3	442.0	636.5

The observations of the authors recorded in Table XI show that the molecular rotation of cinchonidine cinnamate is greater in all solvents under examination than that of the β -phenylpropionate. This indicates that the conversion of a saturated to an ethylenic linking is accompanied by an enhancement in the rotatory power. This is in agreement with observations of earlier workers like Rupe (*Annalen*, 1903, **327**, 157; *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 27, 2796), Pickard and Kenyon (*loc cit.*) and Singh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **117**, 1599).

The authors are grateful to the University of Saugar for providing research facilities and to Dr. O. N. Perti, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Th. D.S.B., Govt. College, Nainital, for making available his manuscript material on strychnine salts.